

THE ANTICOMPETITIVE EFFECT OF MERGERS ON COMPETITION IN TANZANIA AND INDIA

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Abstract: A vibrant and effective competition law framework is essential for the growth of any economy. It helps in regulating a fair market devoid of any anti-competitive practices that cause harm to the customers as well as the business. Competition law is an essential tool to maintain balance in the market by ensuring that any producer will sell his products in the market only at the price which the market is prepared to bear. Also, to ensure there is a perfect competition in the market whereby the producer is the price maker with no capacity to affect the price by his own unilateral action. But then, every good rule can be abused in today's market companies have tried different means to manipulate the end result of competition law. The present study will be looking on whether or not mergers can be used as a tool to manipulate the market and eventually regulate the market cycle.

Keywords: Anti-Competitive, Merger, Competition.

1.0 INTRODUCTION:

The prominent economist Adam Smith¹ has highlighted about the market economy and the role of self-interest and competition as a visible and invisible factor. He argues that most of the economic activity we see around us is the result of self-interest behavior. He says it is not from the kindness of the butcher, the brewer, or the baker that we expect our dinner but from this regard to their own interest. He also argues that competition is the regulator of economic activity, his belief is that competition is the invisible factor, which helps the market to decide about the prices and which tends the manufacture and the seller to be innovative with respect to products and flexible with respect to pricing. In today's economy every company is straggling by using any means to acquire market power. After acquiring that power, they started to misusing their power by controlling the market and fixing the prices. Due to this trend the governments have tried to control them by making the law, but still they devised new strategies against those laws. The first competition law in the World was enacted by Canada in the Year 1889 followed by Sherman Act, 1890 by United States of America. Thereafter, in 1914, the federal trade commission was established through Federal Trade Commission Act, 1914 and the Clayton Act, 1914 was enacted. From there different Antitrust Laws was developed from different part of the World. The system of competition law is generally concerned with practices that are harmful to the competition process in particular competition law is concerned with anti-competitive agreements, abusive behavior, public restriction of competition and mergers. Mergers will be the subject matter of the discussion in this paper.

2.0 COMPETITION LAW AND POLICY

Competition law and Policy form an inherent party of the developing World, it des not only protect the domestic market but also it helps the domestic market to compete fairly and effectively in the international market. Competition law and policy have been very instrumental in fostering sustainable development as well as restricting anti-competitive behavior which inhibit economic growth. Both competition law and policy are used hand in hand, but yet, can be distinguished competition law consists of rules that are intended to protect the process of competition

¹ SAMUEL HOLLANDER, THE ECONOMICS OF ADAM SMITH (University of Toronto Press) (2019)

in order to maximize consumer welfare.² Competition policy however, it has been given different interpretations in different jurisdiction and in different contexts. Essentially, competition policy deals with the scope of public authorities' intervention beyond certain market imperfections, such as market failure. Market failure, in this sense, relates to circumstances in which private forces within the market fail either to sustain desirable activities or to act as a check on undesirable activities carried out by firms. Which necessitate the country to formulate different public policy on competition.³ Moreover, it is certainly that a country's effort to enact a competition law regime can also be termed competition policy.

3.0 HOW IT STARTED IN INDIA: BRIEF HISTORY

It can be traced from 1947 after independent where India started her industrial development. The Industrial Policy Resolution of 1948 manifest the beginning of the evolution of Indian Industrial Policy and afterward with the economic and social development there has been shift in industrial policy from the so called directed and regulated economy in 1948 and 1956 Policy Resolution, to free market economy in 1991. During the epoch of directed and regulated economy in which the government was a biggest business entity and the regulator. Almost every sector was controlled by the government leaving very few spaces for private sector, in order to support that policy Monopolies Restrictive Trade Act, 1969 was enacted. The Act *inter alia* exempts the government corporation and burden private enterprises under the preview of restrictive trade practices and unfair trade practices. The Act further prohibited acquiring of monopoly by private enterprises on a quantitative basis. This led to a lot consequences, there was no competition, which was harmful to economic efficiency and productivity, there was no incentive for cost reduction, Lastly, there was no innovation. As the result the demand of better services and products by the public and for competition in the areas dominated by the government companies. Also, with the winning of liberalization over protectionism in the World influence the government to change its economic law and policy. Raghvan Committee was formed and on its recommendation the Completion Act, 2002 was enacted and competition commission of India was established.

4.0 HOW IT STARTED IN TANZANIA: BRIEF HISTORY

After independence in 1961, the United Republic of Tanzania inherited a market economy system, which prevailed up to 1967, when the Arusha Declaration was made. The Declaration emphasized the self-reliance of the Tanzanian people and collective farming in rural areas and questioned the benefits to the Tanzanian people of foreign or privately owned industries as agents of economic development. The Government nationalized major industries, created cooperatives in the agricultural sector and adopted the Regulation of Prices Act 1973, which set up the National Price Commission. State control was eventually relinquished through structural reforms but the Government still plays a decisive role in how business is conducted in the United Republic of Tanzania. The nationalization of key sectors, such as banking, insurance, pension funds, national retail, agroprocessing and the national transport system, resulted in highly concentrated and monopolized industrial structures. Collective agricultural schemes removed all forms of innovativeness in the agricultural sector, while the State imposed itself as a monopsony buyer, distributor and seller of agricultural produce.⁴ State ownership in most of the key industrial sectors brought about the lack of recapitalization and accountability, and less innovation. Economic stagnation, the oil price shocks of the 1970s and falling prices of the country's main commodity exports contributed to economic decline in the 1980s. Following the resignation of President Nyerere, an economic reform program was introduced. The economic transformation required an overhaul of the whole political and legal system. In 1996, the Government proceeded to review its economic course and formulated the Sustainable Industrial Development Policy 1996–2020, wherein the Government recognized the role of the private sector as the principal vehicle for carrying out direct investment in industry. Competition law In United Republic of Tanzania, it started in 1994, where the first competition law was enacted, the Fair-Trade Practices Act, 1994 and set up a department within the Ministry of Trade and Industry to oversee its implementation. It was replaced by the Fair Competition Act of 2003, which led to the establishment of the more autonomous and independent Fair Competition Commission in 2007. The competition law and policy draw its efficacy from the primary goal of the National Development Vision 2025, the Sustainable Industrial Development Policy and the National Trade Policy, all of which emphasize poverty reduction and eradication through industrialization and an export-led competitive

² RICHARD WHISH & DAVID BAILEY (ATTORNEY), *COMPETITION LAW* (Oxford University Press 10th) (2021)

³ MAHER M. DABBAH, *INTERNATIONAL AND COMPARATIVE COMPETITION LAW* (Cambridge University Press) (2010)

⁴ HELGE KJESHUS, *ECOLOGY CONTROL & ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN EAST AFRICAN HISTORY: THE CASE OF TANGANYIKA 1850-1950* (James Currey) (1996)

economy. Competition policy aims at addressing the problem of concentration of economic power that can arise from market imperfections and monopolistic behavior leading to anticompetitive practices.

5.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Ning Gao, Norman Stronga and Ni Peng⁵ they argue that studying the relation between the wealth effects to merging firms and their corporate customers provides a more informative test of the presence of market power, a negative relation indicating the presence of market power. When we instrument the endogenous wealth effects due to merger announcements, we find that higher abnormal returns to merging firms systematically relate to lower abnormal returns to reliant downstream customers. Further analysis shows that this wealth transfer effect exists for deals in industries that face less foreign competition but not for deals in industries that face intense foreign competition. These results demonstrate the presence of market power (either pre-existing or merger-induced) in merging industries systematically affecting customer value. Finance researchers have disagreed with antitrust authorities for decades on the sources of gains to merging firms in horizontal mergers. For example, Eckbo⁶ he conducted the study on horizontal mergers based on stock market and come up with the findings that no evidence of market power, which conflicts with the frequent concerns of antitrust authorities about the potential for horizontal mergers to harm consumers through market power. He generally concludes that merging firms benefit from efficiency gains or enhanced buying power against suppliers rather than from using market power to expropriate customers. Stafford⁷ he argues that mergers create value for the merging firms. Although the fact that the merging firms' shareholders gain is well documented, in practice, whether mergers generate net benefits to the economy and enhance social welfare is less obvious. Stigler,⁸ argue that mergers facilitate anticompetitive activities and harm consumers. Mitchell and Mulherin⁹ they argues that mergers are driven by efficiency improvement, and bring net benefits to the economy. George Stigler¹⁰ according to him some mergers may result in market power which redounds to the benefit of the merging firms. He argued that such an effect might have been a primary motivation for many of the mergers and acquisitions during the last quarter of the nineteenth century and the first half of the 20th century. He called the 1887-1904 merger wave "mergers for monopoly" and the 1916-1929 wave "mergers for oligopoly." Regardless of whether market power was, or was not, a major motivation for mergers in the first-half of the century, it is doubtful that the bulk of more recent merger activity could be attributed to an effort to secure market power. Dominica Suk-ye Lee¹¹ he conducted the study in Hong Kong to examine whether mergers could help the merging firms to increase their market power and come up with the findings that market share of the merging firms increased significantly to the level comparable with that of the letter group after the mergers. However, according to his study he finds that there is no association between market concentration and market power. Bruce A. Blonigen¹² according to him a fundamental question in the analysis of mergers and acquisition is the potential tradeoff between increased market power and efficient gain. He employs data on mergers and acquisition combined with U.S census plant level data for entire U.S manufacturing sector over 1997 to 2007 period to examine the average impact of mergers and acquisition activity on productivity and mark-ups. He come up with the findings that there is significant evidence of increased markups after mergers and acquisition but no evidence of any average impact on plant- level productivity. Sayan Chattersee¹³ the author conducted the study to investigate the factors that can explain the gains resulting from vertical merger, the finding of the study suggests that acquiring firms gain the most when they come from concentrated market, and the target firms come from fragmented market, the finds also suggest that on the average, the firms studied increased their market power as a result of mergers. Albert Sheen¹⁴ while trying to answer the question why do firms' merge, and what happens when they do, he said merger enable two entities to increase their combined value when brought together in the same firm and the commonly cited as the motivation for pursuing acquisition activity, synergies according to him can take the form of grater

⁵ Ning Gao et al., Market power in horizontal mergers: Evidence from wealth transfers between merging firms and their customers, (2015)

⁶ Espen Eckbo, Mergers and the Value of Antitrust Deterrence, 47 THE JOURNAL OF FINANCE 1005–1029 (1992)

⁷ Gregor Andrade et al., New Evidence and Perspectives on Mergers, 15 JOURNAL OF ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVES 103–120 (2001)

⁸ George J. Stigler, A Theory of Oligopoly, 72 JOURNAL OF POLITICAL ECONOMY 44–61 (1964)

⁹ Gregor Andrade et al., New Evidence and Perspectives on Mergers, 15 THE JOURNAL OF ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVES 103–120 (2001)

¹⁰ [CSL STYLE ERROR: reference with no printed form.]

¹¹ Dominica Suk-ye Lee, The Impact of the Big 8 Mergers on Market Power: Evidence from the Hong Kong Market, 16 JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT AND ACCOUNTING 69–96 (2005)

¹² Bruce A. Blonigen & Justin R. Pierce, Evidence for the Effects of Mergers on Market Power and Efficiency, 2016 FINANCE AND ECONOMICS DISCUSSION SERIES (2016), <https://www.federalreserve.gov/econres/feds/evidence-for-the-effects-of-mergers-on-market-power-and-efficiency.htm> (last visited Nov 7, 2021)

¹³ OLIVIER FURRER, CORPORATE LEVEL STRATEGY: THEORY AND APPLICATIONS (Routledge) (2016)

¹⁴ Albert Sheen, The Real Product Market Impact of Mergers: The Real Product Market Impact of Mergers, 69 THE JOURNAL OF FINANCE 2651–2688 (2014)

revenues through channels such as market power or new product introduction, or lost reduction through efficiency gains from consolidating plants or suppliers.

In nutshell, a key question is whether mergers increase the market power of the merging firms, according to the reviewed literature, the answer to this question cannot be direct, it requires critical examination and reviews of the available literature so as to come up with the concrete response. Since some of the study shows that post-merger really enhances market power. In summary, most academic studies have indicated that market power are positively related to merger activity.

6.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The doctrinaire approach has been adopted in researching for this work. Different books, article and Legislations from different jurisdiction around the world have been used in preparing this paper.

6.1 VARIABLES:

- Market Cycles
- Mergers.

6.2 OBJECTIVE OF THE RESEARCH

Assess whether or not mergers enhance market power which eventually regulate the market cycle: boom and bust.

6.3 INDEPENDENT VARIABLES.

- Mergers

6.4 DEPENDENT VARIABLES

- Market Cycles: Boom and Bust

6.5 HYPOTHESIS

Mergers enhance market power which eventually regulate the market cycle.

6.6 RESEARCH QUESTION

Do Market Cycle: boom and bust regulated by Mergers which have Market power?

6.7 RESEARCH DESIGN

Correlation research design, this design will be used to examine the relationship between mergers and market cycle. I will be looking on both relational statements and causal statement. Whereby the former is about the association between dependent and independent variables and try to see whether there is some kind of influence of one on the other, while the later which will also be referred to as cause-and-effect relationship, whereby the cause will be referred to as dependent variable and the variable that is affected is referred to as independent variable.

7.0 DISCUSSION ON MERGERS AND MARKET POWER

Mergers is the combination of two companies into one company where one company loses its identity. A true merger involves two separate undertakings merging entirely into a new entity.¹⁵ However, the expression merger as used in competition policy is all about looking the possibility that a merger will lead to the market being less competitive in the future that is currently is. This concern was first introduced under Section 7 of the Clayton Act, 1914 which regulate corporate mergers accusing only those mergers whose effect may be substantially to lessen competition or tends to creates monopoly. However, before concluding that certain merged company has the effect of reduce competition or there is a likelihood of creating monopoly there must be a clear proof of market power, in fact the main purpose of section 7 of Clayton Act is to limit mergers that increase market power. After that observation the question comes how to prove that post- merger enhances market power or in other words after merger firm really acquire market power, there are different issue to be considered, market shares and concentration level of the market, but first of all relevant market must be defined. Therefore, defining relevant market makes possible to measure the market power of the merged firm. Concrete evaluation will be done in the coming part.

¹⁵ RICHARD WHISH & DAVID BAILEY, COMPETITION LAW (Oxford University Press 7th ed) (2012)

8.0 MERGER LAW AND MARKET STRUCTURE

Merger laws are primarily related with the regulation of market structure. Almost all competition law regimes seek to regulate market structure. Aspect of market structure that is regulated by competition law is market concentration, although merger laws are usually designed to address behavioral considerations jointly as well. Market concentration measures the number of firms within the market and their relative market shares. The level of market concentration provides useful proxy for the likely intensity of market competition.¹⁶ The concern of competition law is that a high degree of market concentration may be associated with increased market power, reduced competition and reduced competitive constraints on existing firms. It may arise in different ways, first, higher concentration may result in an individual post-merger firm having excessive market power. Such high levels of market power may enable more powerful firms to acquire greater producer surplus at the expense of consumer surplus and total economic welfare. Secondly, higher concentration may result in an increased likelihood of the post-merger firm to co-operating either expressly or tacitly with other firms so that together they can reduce quantity supplied into the market, particularly in more concentrated oligopolistic market structure. Merger law is the primarily mechanism used by most nations to regulate market structure. They are framed so as to prohibit a firm from acquiring an asset or business where the acquisition would unduly increase the market power of that firm.

9.0 MARKET POWER VERSUS EFFICIENT EFFECT OF MERGERS

Essential question here is effect of mergers and acquisition activity in the market and perhaps the most important issue is the potential tradeoff between increased market power versus efficiency gain. Changes in the market power and efficiency due to mergers and acquisition has a direct implication on welfare, however, is difficult to draw a clear line between market power and efficiency as the outcome of mergers. There exist ambiguities on the reviewed literatures there a number of studies which was conducted on the same set of facts but every study come up with its own findings and conclusion. On top of that uncertainties there exists also a debate among economists argue that competition authorities should take efficiency gains into account when examining merger cases rather than the anticompetitive effect of merger (market power). According to the economists Williamson¹⁷ one among the advocate of this thought that merger control should take efficiency gains rather than market power it creates, he believing that if efficiency created by merger is more than outweigh market power effect and if those efficiencies are passed on to the consumer, then price may decrease and consumer welfare increases. This long debate has led me to discuss the schools of economics in relation mergers.

10.0 DISCUSSION OF MERGERS IN VIEW OF HARVARD SCHOOL AND CHICAGO SCHOOL IN A NUTSHELL

The economic theories of a group of Harvard scholars assumed that firms with market power would act in an anticompetitive manner.¹⁸ Under the "Harvard School" approach, any mergers that allowed firms to obtain, enhance, or exercise market power, regardless of whether the conduct had the potential to benefit consumers by lowering prices or increasing output is illegal. The theories of a group of University of Chicago on the other hand, they taught that the only legitimate goal of the antitrust laws was to promote consumer welfare.¹⁹ Under the "Chicago School" approach, mergers cannot be judged sole on the ground that they enhance market power. Instead, they felt compelled to engage in an extensive factual inquiry to confirm the effects of particular conduct on consumers before finding it illegal.

As have already discuss prior that there exists a debate among economists on the effect of mergers, the debate of which we can categories as the Harvard school and Chicago school. Chicago school they say there is no correlation between high concentration and bad economic outcome, they don't consumer welfare as the end, they see efficiency as the end. To them merger which create higher price for consumer but also create greater efficiency to merging firms that kind of merger should not be discouraged because the goal of competition policy to them is efficiency and if consumer welfare and efficiency come onto conflict, efficiency is he greatest good. To be more precise to them if merger is anti-competitive but create efficiency that merger is good. Harvard school on the other hand, argued that an industry's structure, that is, the number of firms in the market and their relative sizes, determines how effectively firms will perform in that market, they postulate further when markets are concentrated, firms are more likely to engage in anticompetitive conduct. Harvard scholars opposed market concentration, even when it might lower costs and prices,

¹⁶ MARTYN D. TAYLOR, *INTERNATIONAL COMPETITION LAW: A NEW DIMENSION FOR THE WTO?* (Cambridge University Press) (2006)

¹⁷ Oliver E. Williamson, *Economies as an Antitrust Defense: The Welfare Tradeoffs*, 58 *THE AMERICAN ECONOMIC REVIEW* 18–36 (1968)

¹⁸ Thomas A Piraino Jr, *Reconciling the Harvard and Chicago Schools: A New Antitrust Approach for the 21st Century*, 82 *INDIANA LAW JOURNAL* 67

¹⁹ Thomas A Piraino Jr, *Reconciling the Harvard and Chicago Schools: A New Antitrust Approach for the 21st Century*, 82 *INDIANA LAW JOURNAL* 67

thereby benefiting consumers. A point to note here is that neither Harvard school nor Chicago school has suggested directly that mergers enhance market power and either the two school has disputed the same. But I have discussed these two schools here to show a reflection on how mergers have been discussed on these two important thoughts on competition law of any jurisdiction.

11.0 TANZANIA AND INDIA LEGAL FRAMEWORK IN REFLECTION TO THE SCHOOLS SPECIFICALLY ON MERGERS

In India the Commission, after having made investigation and enquiries, may approve the combination if in its opinion it does not or likely to have an appreciable adverse effect on competition and the test whether a merger is to be permitted or not is to be based, *inter alia*, on the expected impact of the merger on market power and competition in the relevant market. Also, given the size and growth of the market and the presence or absence of entry barriers, an assessment of how the market is expected to evolve.²⁰ In Tanzania core elements of competition law are prohibition of anticompetitive agreements, mergers, misuse of market power and consumer protection, a person shall not make or give effect to an agreement if the object, effect or likely effect of the agreement is to appreciably prevent, restrict or distort competition.²¹ A firm is considered to have market power if when acting alone, the person can profitably and materially restrain or reduce competition in that market for a significant period of time and the firm's share of the relevant market exceeds 35 per cent.²² The substantive test is that a merger is prohibited if it creates or strengthens a position of dominance in a market, of which dominance has a 35 per cent threshold.²³ To be more precisely both Tanzania and India competition laws has been constructed in the view of Harvard school of thought. Even if mergers actually enhance efficiency but it would lead to a 35 per cent market share that merger should be prohibited.

12.0 MERGERS ENHANCES MARKET POWER WHICH EVENTUALLY REGULATE MARKET CYCLE

Up to this point it is clear enough to say that truly mergers enhance market power. However, the fact that the firm that a firm merely possess market power is not in itself a competition law violation, market power is a necessary element of monopoly. While monopoly power is defined as the power to control price or exclude competition. Market power means the ability of influence the price; market power enhances monopoly. To be more precisely, a firm is a monopolist or is considered to possess market power if it can profitably raise prices substantially above the competitive level. So, from this observation a merged firm that has subsequently acquired market power post-merger can regulate the market cycle.

According to the U.S merger guidelines for the assessment of anticompetitive effect of merger involves two stage, namely first defining relevant market, secondly identifying the size of the firms involved in relevant market, once this has been identified then premerger and post-merger market power can be calculated. The post-merger can be obtained by considering that, after the merger, the merging firms' market share will be the sum of their premerger market share. According to Alison Jones and Brenda Sufirin²⁴ they say there are two ways of measuring a firm's market power, direct and indirect. The direct method according to them is estimating market power by using econometric methods, the demand curve, the indirect method however, is the structural approach where first relevant market is defined and, second the power on that market of the undertaking under review is assessed using market share and barriers to entry analysis. According to them barriers to entry are vital to the determination of market power by this method since it is these which enable a firm already in the market to earn monopoly profits without attracting other form to enter that market. The indirect method is the most commonly used by competition authorities in the certain jurisdictions around the World. Under the indirect method the size of the firm's market share is the starting point for assessing market power both in absolute terms and relative to those of its competitors. In this formula a point to note is that a market share of more than 50 percent may indicate dominance where competitor holds a much smaller share of the market. However, market power cannot be determined on the basis of market share figure alone.²⁵ Merger enhances market power if it is likely to encourage one or more firms to raise price, reduce output, diminish innovation, or otherwise harm customers as a result of diminished competitive constraints or incentives. In order to come up with my own conclusion that truly mergers enhance market power mergers have been investigated to see their status of market power in pre- and post-merger.

²⁰ SECTION 6 (3) Read together with SECTION 29 OF THE COMPETITION ACT, 2002

²¹ SECTION 8 OF THE COMPETITION ACT, 2003

²² SECTION 60 OF THE FAIR COMPETITION ACT, 2003

²³ SECTION 11 OF THE FAIR COMPETITION ACT, 2003

²⁴ ALISON JONES ET AL., JONES & SUFRIN'S EU COMPETITION LAW: TEXT, CASES, AND MATERIALS (Oxford University Press Seventh Edition) (2019)

²⁵ RICHARD WHISH & DAVID BAILEY (ATTORNEY), COMPETITION LAW (Oxford University Press 10th Ed) (2021)

13.0 PRE- AND POST-MERGER ON MARKET POWER

For instance, in the Mango Juice market there are 4 competitors, whereby 2 of the each has a market share of 30 per cent, and the other 2 has the market share of 20 per cent. Let's evaluate this example in premerger and post-merger point of view. In premerger market concentration is low and there are clear indications of perfect competition among the competitors in the fruits market. However, in the same example let's say if firm A which has 30 per cent market share decides to merge with firm B which has also 30 per cent market share what will happen. So, there will be 3 competitors whereby 1 has 60 per cent market share and the other 2 has 40 per cent market share. In the second illustration merger has enhances market power. Market shares can directly influence firms' competitive incentives. The Merged firm may reduce price in order to gain new customers also a firm with a large market share may be more reluctant to implement a price reduction than one with a small share. Likewise, a firm with a large market share may not feel pressure to reduce price even if a smaller rival does. Market shares also can reflect firms' capabilities. For example, a firm with a large market share may be able to expand output rapidly by a larger absolute amount than can a small firm. Similarly, a large market share tends to indicate low costs, an attractive product, or both. To be more precise post-merger led to market power of the merged firm. The merged firm is in position to affect the market price, since it is responsible for all the output and since it is the aggregate output that determines price through the relationship of supply to demand, the merged firms can control the show the way they want either by increase price by reducing the volume of its own production or to reduce sales by increase price. Enhanced market power in this example can also be manifested in non-price terms and conditions that adversely affect customers, including reduced product quality, reduced product variety, reduced service, or diminished innovation. Such non-price effects may coexist with price effects, or can arise in their absence. Enhanced market power may also make it more likely that the merged entity can profitably and effectively engage in exclusionary conduct. Regardless of how enhanced market power likely would be manifested. In evaluating market power, we have to consider both the post-merger situation and the change in concentration resulting from a merger. Market shares may not fully reflect the competitive significance of firms in the market or the impact of a merger.

14.0 MERGER AND MARKET CYCLE

Most studies of mergers have apparently concluded that mergers are timed closely with the market cycle, there is no causal relationship between mergers and market cycle but, a point to note is that each merger possess unique picture.

15.0 CONCLUSION

The probability of the merged firms acquiring market power after merger and as a result thereof impeding the effective competition within the relevant market is very high. There is a causal relationship between mergers and market power, in the sense that mergers cause market power, however the study shows that there is no causal relationship between mergers and market cycle, the study shows that here is association between these two variables. In this sense therefore, the hypothesis is partly negative and partly positive. The merging parties' market shares in a relevant market, the level of concentration, and the change in concentration caused by the merger that cause a significant increase in concentration and result in highly concentrated markets are presumed to be likely to enhance market power. A merger can enhance market power simply by eliminating competition between the merging parties. This effect can arise even if the merger causes no changes in the way other firms behave. Merger also can enhance market power by increasing the risk of coordinated, accommodating, or interdependent behavior among rivals. In any given case, either or both types of effects may be present, and the distinction between them may be blurred. After all of this there is no any conclusion to the effect that mergers that have market power regulate market cycle.

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